

Dynamic photo-physiological responses of the dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis* to short-term changes in temperature and nitrogen substrates

So Hyun (Sophia) Ahn^{1*}, Patricia M. Glibert¹, Cynthia A. Heil²

¹ University of Maryland Center for Environmental Science, Horn Point Laboratory, PO Box 775, Cambridge, MD 21613, United States; ² Mote Marine Laboratory, 1600 Ken Thompson Pkwy, Sarasota, FL 34236, United States.

* corresponding author's email: sahn@umces.edu

Abstract

On the West Florida Shelf, annual blooms of the neurotoxin-producing harmful dinoflagellate, *Karenia brevis* (and other *Karenia* species) cause negative effects on the environment, the economy, and on human health. Blooms primarily occur in the fall months and may overwinter into winter and spring, but they rarely persist throughout the hot summer months when water temperatures are above 30°C. During 2020 and 2021, an unusually prolonged (~12 months) *K. brevis* bloom occurred. During the early phase of this bloom (January, 2021) when *K. brevis* were present in low-moderate abundances in southwest Florida, experiments on rates of photosynthesis were conducted on surface samples from two offshore stations within the bloom. Photosynthesis-irradiance responses were examined using PAM fluorometry to assess responses to varying nitrogen conditions and temperatures. Treatments included controls and exposures to temperatures of 15, 20, 25, 30°C with and without 10 µM additions of three nitrogen forms (nitrate, ammonium, urea). Although there were variations between stations, in general decreasing trends of fluorescence parameters with increasing temperature from 15°C to 30°C were observed, suggesting that 30°C might be physiologically stressful for *Karenia*. However, when cells were treated with urea, this reduction was substantially less. These results suggest *K. brevis* dependence on nitrogen form may change with temperature, and availability of chemically-reduced organic forms of nitrogen may be favored at the highest temperatures that *Karenia* may experience.

Keywords: *Karenia brevis*, PAM fluorometry, Fv/Fm, ETR, nitrogen, urea, photosynthesis, temperature

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Introduction

On the West Florida Shelf (WFS), the toxic dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis* forms red tides almost annually (e.g., Heil *et al.*, 2014a). The location, magnitude, and duration of blooms vary every year and are linked to environmental factors in a complex manner. While both state monitoring and focused research efforts have led to considerable understanding about the ecology and physiology of *K. brevis* (Kusek *et al.*, 1999; Heil *et al.*, 2014b and references therein), many critical questions regarding the physiology of *K. brevis* under different environmental conditions remain unanswered.

Temperature, nutrients, and light are three important environmental factors regulating the physiology of *K. brevis* (Heil *et al.*, 2014a, b). Temperature has long been considered a significant factor affecting *Karenia* bloom dynamics on WFS. Although factors underlying bloom initiation interact in a complicated manner, temperature is considered an important factor in determining whether blooms are likely to occur (Kusek *et al.*, 1999). Blooms rarely persist throughout the summer months, when water temperatures can be above 30°C. Laboratory experiments have shown a temperature optimum of 22-28°C (e.g., Vargo *et al.*, 2009), the lack of summer blooms has been suggested to be due, at least in part, to high temperatures. Temperature not only affects growth, but it also affects the metabolism of different forms of nitrogen (N) differently (e.g., Glibert *et al.*, 2016). These patterns could be species-specific but, in general, the enzyme involved in nitrate (NO₃⁻) metabolism, NO₃⁻ reductase, has an inverse relationship with temperature over the range from 15-30°C (Lomas and

Glibert, 1999a, b). In contrast, the enzymes involved in the assimilation of chemically reduced nitrogen, ammonium (NH₄⁺), glutamine synthetase and glutamate synthase, and of urea, urease, tend to show positive relationships with temperature over this same temperature range (Lomas and Glibert, 1999 a, b; Fan *et al.*, 2003; Glibert *et al.*, 2016). Although it is an obligate autotroph, *K. brevis* can use many different forms of N, including NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, and urea (Glibert *et al.*, 2009; Bronk *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, multiple N sources available on WFS such as nutrients from freshwater and estuarine flows, and regenerated nutrients from dead fish could support *K. brevis* blooms simultaneously (Heil *et al.*, 2014a). This dinoflagellate can also obtain nutrition via mixotrophy (Glibert *et al.*, 2009).

Blooms of *K. brevis* initiate offshore and may be transported to the WFS via upwelling (Weisberg and He, 2003; Weisberg *et al.*, 2014). Generally, *K. brevis* densities on the WFS start to increase in late summer and can remain high during fall and winter when surface water temperatures can be low as ~15°C. Cell densities tend to decrease during late spring and rarely persist through the hot summer when temperatures are higher than 30°C (Brand and Compton, 2007). Vertical gradients in temperatures of > 5-10°C may also exist throughout the year on WFS (Weisberg and He, 2003; Weisberg *et al.*, 2014). Thus, *K. brevis*, which vertically migrates, can be subject to abrupt changes in temperature and possibly to co-occurring changes in N forms and light conditions. Here, the short-term interactions of temperature, N forms, and light on photosynthetic performance of the

winter *Karenia* community were examined to understand how these responses may relate to the conditions under which the *Karenia* community is found on WFS.

Material and Methods

Bloom sampling and experimental setup

Near-surface water samples were collected from two offshore stations (15S, 26.3896 N, -81.9800 W and 19S, 26.28625 N, -82.34284 W) on January 22nd, 2021. Ambient water temperature was measured using a Seabird 19 plus V2 package. Water was returned to the lab within two h and manipulation experiments were immediately initiated. Water from each station was first transferred to 50 mL polypropylene tubes. Nutrient additions (10 μ M of NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , or urea) were added to four tubes from each station and four unamended tubes from each station served as controls. Subsequently, one set of tubes from each station, including a control, and one each enriched with either NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , or urea, were placed in four different temperature-controlled water baths (15, 20, 25, 30°C) and incubated for one hour under 100 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Chlorophyll a, nutrient and K. brevis cell concentrations

Immediately upon return to the laboratory, water samples were filtered through pre-combusted (450°C, 2-3 h) Whatman GF/F filters for chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) determination. The filtrates were frozen in brown bottles for subsequent measurements of NO_3^- + nitrite (NO_2^-), NH_4^+ , urea, and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) via autoanalyzer at the Mote Marine Laboratory. Additionally, 5 mL of each bloom water was fixed with acidic Lugol's solution and *K.*

brevis concentrations were determined by light microscopy.

Experimental photosynthetic responses

To assess the photosynthetic response of the samples exposed to different nutrient and temperatures, *in vivo* Chl *a* fluorescence was measured using a Phyto-PAM-II multi-excitation wavelength chlorophyll fluorometer (Heinz Walz GmbH, Effeltrich, Germany). With appropriate calibration and deconvolution of fluorescence signals, this instrument can measure the photosynthetic responses of four different major classes of algae, including cyanobacteria, green algae, brown algae, and phycoerythrin -containing cells with a single measurement. The brown algal signal includes both diatoms and dinoflagellates, but microscopic analyses confirmed that the dominant organism present in the samples measured in this category was *K. brevis*.

After one hour of incubation, samples were dark-adapted for 20 min and Rapid Light Curves were conducted using twelve incremental irradiance steps (0, 6, 24, 42, 73, 109, 188, 227, 334, 489, 591, 719 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The maximum photochemical efficiency of photosystem II (PS II) was calculated as $F_v/F_m = (F_m - F_o)/F_m$ where F_v is the variable fluorescence, F_o is the minimal fluorescence, and F_m is the maximum fluorescence. The maximum relative electron transport rates ($rETR_{\text{max}}$) were calculated from $rETR$ versus irradiance curves using the Platt *et al.* (1980) equation. Statistical analyses of fluorescence parameters were performed using R.

Results and Discussion

Both stations were characterized by low inorganic nutrient concentrations (Table 1). The Chl *a* concentration was four-fold lower and the phaeophytin/Chl *a* (Phaeo/Chl *a*) ratio was higher at station 19S compared to station 15S (Table 1). Ambient temperature at the time of sampling was 20°C.

Table 1. Concentrations of Chl *a* ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and nutrients (μM). Urea was not detectable.

	Station 15S	Station 19S
Chl <i>a</i>	10.5	2.4
Phaeo/Chl <i>a</i>	0.23	0.4
$\text{NO}_3^- + \text{NO}_2^-$	< 0.07	< 0.07
NH_4^+	0.23	0.15
PO_4^{3-}	0.20	0.05

Both stations had a mixed phytoplankton community composition, with substantial *K. brevis* abundance. Station 15S was dominated by dinoflagellates (220,000 cell L^{-1}) and 94% of the dinoflagellate population was *K. brevis*. At station 19S, approximately 30% of the algae was dominated by dinoflagellates (20,000 cell L^{-1}) (Fig. 1), of which 75% were *K. brevis*. Neither station had more than a small percentage of diatoms (6%). Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that most of the fluorescence signals of the brown algae originated from *K. brevis* during this study.

Fig. 1. Phytoplankton composition at two stations during January 22nd, 2021 on WFS.

In general, decreasing trends of the maximum quantum yields of PSII photochemical efficiency, F_v/F_m , were observed in each N treatment as temperature increased from 15°C to 30°C although only the data from station 15S were significantly different (ANOVA, $p < 0.5$) (Figs. 2a, b). However, this trend was less consistent when cells were treated with urea. The $rETR_{max}$ also showed similar trends with F_v/F_m (Figs. 1c, d). Although the differences were less at station 19S, generally $rETR_{max}$ also decreased with increasing temperature except for the urea-treated samples.

In both field and laboratory cultures, *K. brevis* has been observed in the range of 7-33°C, but the optimum temperature range has previously been reported to be relatively narrow, 22-28°C (Kusek *et al.*, 1999). The decline of fluorescence parameters after even one hour exposure to 30°C in this study suggests that this high temperature is stressful for the winter *Karenia* community. However, when bloom water was enriched with urea, fluorescence parameters were

Fig. 2. Fv/Fm and rETR_{max} ($\mu\text{mol electrons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) of *K. brevis* exposed to different temperatures (15, 20, 25, 30°C) and nitrogen ($10 \mu\text{M NO}_3^-$; NH_4^+ or urea) additions. The color bars increase in brightness from 15°C to 30°C at each treatment.

reduced to a lesser degree (Fig. 2), implying that urea might induce a photoprotective mechanism. Dinoflagellates have a urea cycle that helps in the reallocation of intracellular carbon (C) and N (Dagenais-Bellefeuille *et al.*, 2013) and in *Karenia mikimotoi*, several enzymes involved in the urea cycle have been identified (Shi *et al.*, 2021). The increased recycling of C and N from catabolism and photorespiration through the urea cycle could enhance overall metabolic flux, thus increasing the demand for chemical energy to run metabolism. To match this demand, a higher proportion of absorbed light energy may be channeled to photochemical reactions, therefore increasing Fv/Fm and rETR. In addition, urease, the enzyme involved in urea metabolism, generally has a positive relationship with temperature (Fan *et al.*,

2003). Therefore, when urea is available at 30°C, high temperature stress might be partly alleviated by balancing light energy demand. At 15°C, which is lower than the optimal temperature range for *K. brevis*, the photosynthetic performance of winter *Karenia* communities was not significantly reduced compared to those temperatures close to, or at, optimal temperatures and some fluorescence parameters (e.g., Fv/Fm) were even higher at this cool temperature (Fig. 2). The winter *Karenia* community, which was adapted to cool ambient water temperatures at the time of sampling, were able to operate their photosynthetic apparatus efficiently at 15°C. Compared to station 15S populations, cells at station 19S did not respond significantly to N pulses, even though ambient N concentration was very low. However, the *K. brevis* cells from this station may have been physiologically less active, as indicated by the higher Phaeo/Chl *a* ratio (Table 1), suggesting that *K. brevis* at station 19S would be less photosynthetic active.

Overall, these results indicate the photosynthetic response of *K. brevis* to changes in N supply may vary with temperature and suggest that the pull of metabolism may buffer the stress of high light, but that the extent of this photoprotection mechanism depends on N form.

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